

Analysis of the Heuristic Algorithms Application for Route Optimization of a Medical Robot Assistant

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Abstract

This study explores the application of heuristic algorithms to the salesman problem solution for optimizing the mobile robot assistant's route. Utilizing the branch-and-bound method for exact solutions and heuristic methods such as simulated annealing and the ant algorithm, the research assesses their performance across networks of different sizes. Simulation results reveal the ant algorithm's superior efficiency for smaller networks (up to 100 nodes), outperforming simulated annealing in terms of average route length and calculation time. However, scalability challenges emerge with larger networks (500 nodes). Detailed algorithm parameters are presented, emphasizing the significance of tailored settings for optimal performance. The study concludes that while heuristic algorithms are advantageous for rapid route generation, exact algorithms are preferred for precision, offering insights for route planning optimization for a medical robot assistant.

Keywords ¹

Ant algorithm, heuristic algorithms, medical robot assistant, route optimization, simulated annealing algorithm, traveling salesman problem

Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of healthcare, the integration of robotic technologies has emerged as a promising frontier, particularly in the domain of medical assistance. The deployment of mobile medical robots has shown significant potential in enhancing the efficiency and precision of various healthcare tasks, ranging from drug delivery to patient monitoring. One critical aspect influencing the effectiveness of these robots is the optimization of their routes within medical environments [1].

This study focuses on a comparative analysis of the heuristic algorithms applied to the problem of medical robot assistants route optimization as a salesman's problem. Heuristic algorithms, known for their ability to find near-optimal solutions in a timely manner [2], play a pivotal role in addressing the complex spatial and temporal constraints inherent in medical settings. The optimization of routes is of paramount importance, as it directly influences the robot's ability to navigate dynamically changing environments, interact seamlessly with medical staff, and deliver services with maximum efficiency.

As the demand for modern medical robotics continues to grow, understanding the performance and adaptability of heuristic algorithms becomes extremely important [3]. This research aims to examine the practical aspects of applying heuristic algorithms in the context of route optimization for medical robot assistants. The results obtained can help in the development and implementation of more efficient and faster medical robotic systems.

Through this analysis, we aim to facilitate informed decision-making in the design and implementation of medical robot assistants, fostering progress that is in line with the changing landscape of modern healthcare.

Methods and Results

The objective of this study is to compare the exact solution of the traveling salesman problem obtained by the method of branches and boundaries and the approximate solution obtained by heuristic methods. The exact solution was used to estimate the error of heuristic solutions [4]. Determining the error of the solution allowed us to determine the number of iterations required, and thus to estimate the time to obtain a valid solution [5].

The traveling salesman problem was solved using the branch-and-bound method in MATLAB for a network of 10 and 30 nodes. The distance between the routers in the network was chosen as the cost of the connection, which was modeled by a uniform distribution in the range of (1-100) m and a normal distribution with a mathematical expectation of 5 m and a variance of 1 m². The optimal route of the mobile agent was considered to be the route of minimum length. The sample average of the optimal route length over 500 experiments was considered as the result of the experiment. The non-optimized route was considered on the set of all permutations of network nodes.

To confirm the reliability of the sample averages, recursive estimates of the route length of a mobile agent were obtained using the Robbins-Monroe procedure [6]. Recursive estimates of the route length using optimization and without optimization are shown in Figs. 1-2.

Figure 1: Recursive estimation of the mobile agent's route length with a normal distribution of distances between nodes, $n = 10$.

Figure 2: Recursive estimation of the mobile agent's route length with a normal distribution of distances between nodes, $n = 30$.

Two heuristic algorithms were chosen for comparison: the simulated annealing algorithm and the ant algorithm. To apply the algorithms to solve the salesman's problem, the coordinates of the points were set. Fig. 3 shows the minimum route for 20 points.

Parameters for the ant algorithm:

- Number of iterations (generations) - 55
- Number of ants per generation - 10
- Number of points - 20
- α (coefficient of orientation to pheromones) - 1
- β (coefficient of orientation to the length of the route) - 2
- p (local pheromone renewal coefficient) - 0.1
- e (global pheromone renewal coefficient) - 0.1
- q (coefficient of selection of the most attractive item) - 0.9
- the initial location of ants is random.

The average route length was 357.4470 units, the average simulation time was 0.3112 seconds, and the average error was 0.0319 %.

Parameters for the simulated annealing algorithm:

Number of points - 20

Initial temperature - 1000

Final temperature - 0.1

Temperature formula - initial temperature / k-th iteration

Number of iterations - 250000

Acceptance probability function - $\exp(-\Delta E / T)$

The average route length was 367.5737 units, the average simulation time was 0.5230 seconds, and the average error was 2.8659 %.

Figure 3: Minimal route for 20 nodes.

As can be seen from the simulation, for 20 nodes, the ant algorithm performed better than the simulated annealing algorithm, both in terms of average route and calculation time. For the simulated annealing algorithm, the number of iterations or the initial temperature can be reduced, which in turn will reduce the calculation time, but at the same time, the accuracy of the calculations themselves will decrease.

Figure 4 shows the minimum route for 50 nodes.

Parameters for the ant algorithm:

- Number of iterations (generations) - 3900
- Number of ants per generation - 10
- Number of points - 50
- α (coefficient of orientation to pheromones) - 1
- β (coefficient of orientation to the length of the route) - 2
- p (local pheromone renewal coefficient) - 0.1
- e (global pheromone renewal coefficient) - 0.1
- q (coefficient of selection of the most attractive item) - 0.9

- initial location of ants - random
- The average route length (units) was 571.8715, the average modulation time (seconds) was 27.1727, and the average error (%) was 0.5264
- Parameters for the simulated annealing algorithm:
- Number of points - 50
- Initial temperature - 100000
- Final temperature - 0.1
- Temperature formula - initial temperature / k-th iteration
- Number of iterations - 250000
- Acceptance probability function - $\exp(-\Delta E / T)$

Figure 4: Minimal route for 50 nodes.

The average route length (units) was 572.6818, the average modulation time (seconds) was 42.6522, and the average error (%) was 0.6689.

The results of calculations for 100 and 500 points are shown in Table 1.

Table 1

Simulation results for 100 and 500 nodes

Sample No	Ant algorithm		Simulated annealing	
	Route length (units)	Time (seconds)	Route length (units)	Time (seconds)
100 nodes				
1	821.4988	189.513869	817.5347	42.239714
2	816.6737	186.088802	801.4941	43.638596
3	799.4715	140.772230	800.1126	48.471429
500 nodes				
1	∞	∞	1836.4	79.681766
2	∞	∞	1843.1	83.506554

Based on the simulation, we can conclude that the ant algorithm performs better for all criteria with a small number of nodes (up to 100). With a larger number of nodes, the execution time of the ant algorithm increases significantly. Therefore, its use in calculating a route with a large number of nodes is not reasonable.

It is shown that the use of heuristic algorithms is advisable only in cases where it is necessary to quickly generate a new route for a mobile agent. When the speed of generating a new route is not critical, it is better to use exact route calculation algorithms. For each algorithm, it is necessary to select parameters depending on the task, since these parameters affect the speed of the algorithm and can reduce the range of possible routes that can be obtained during calculations.

As calculations have shown, the introduction of optimization procedures when choosing a mobile agent's route in WSNs leads to a decrease in the length of the traversal loop in the range of 30%-40% compared to the non-optimized route, depending on the law of arc length distribution.

Conclusions

A comparative analysis of the exact solution of the traveling salesman problem obtained by the method of branches and boundaries and the approximate solution obtained by heuristic methods is carried out. To obtain an approximate solution, two heuristic algorithms were programmed: the ant algorithm and the simulated annealing algorithm, which were implemented in MATLAB. The ant algorithm and the burning simulation algorithm were implemented for the traveling salesman problem with 10, 20, and 50 nodes with specific coordinates for each problem.

The study observed that the ant algorithm performed better for smaller networks (up to 100 nodes), surpassing simulated annealing in terms of criteria such as route length and calculation time.

However, with a larger number of nodes (500), the execution time of the ant algorithm increased significantly, indicating limitations in scalability.

Heuristic algorithms, particularly the ant algorithm, were deemed advisable for scenarios where rapid route generation for a mobile medical robot assistant is crucial.

For situations where speed is not critical, exact route calculation algorithms were recommended, as they offer more precise solutions.

The selection of algorithm parameters is crucial and should align with the specific task requirements to optimize algorithm speed and solution accuracy.

The results obtained can help in the development and implementation of more efficient and faster medical robotic systems.

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